

THE NECESSITIES OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES FOR THE UZBEK YOUNGSTERS IN THE MODERN WORLD

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Abstract: the article analyzes the need to study foreign languages for the Uzbek youngsters in modern society. It also examines the role of linguistic diversity in society, various thoughts of foreign scientists on the issues of studying foreign languages and factors that provoke the study of foreign languages.

Аннотация: В статье анализируется необходимость изучения иностранных языков узбекской молодёжью в современном обществе. Также рассматриваются роль языкового разнообразия в обществе, различные взгляды зарубежных учёных на проблемы изучения иностранных языков и факторы, побуждающие к изучению иностранных языков.

Keywords: learning a foreign language, cultural value, traditions of diverse nations, necessities of studying foreign languages, motives for studying a foreign language.

Ключевые слова: изучение иностранного языка, культурные ценности, традиции разных народов, необходимость изучения иностранных языков, мотивы изучения иностранного языка.

Learning a foreign language in the modern world is one of the most essential components of life of a modern, successful person in each country and Uzbekistan is not an exception in this case. Knowledge of a foreign language is not just an optional choice, it is necessary for all the Uzbek young. Nowadays, more and more people who want to know a foreign language, have new opportunities and this leads to enrich their spiritual world. It can be noted that our great ancestor, Al-Farabi could speak more than 70 languages discovering a lot of investigations in astronomy, math, philosophy. Al-Farabi clarified the essence of humanity's acquisition of knowledge. Sensation alone is not enough to understand the essence. This can only be achieved with the help of reason.

Learning foreign languages is a creative, exciting activity that widens a worldview, allows one to improve critical thinking, and the ability to express one`s thoughts briefly and in detail. Ideally, an educated, ambitious person

should speak several foreign languages, constantly develop and improve them, as learning foreign languages is not a monotonous process at all [1]. Therefore, in Uzbekistan the opportunities for youngsters to study foreign languages are being developed by the government.

Learning a foreign language is not as easy as it may seem at first glance. It is a long and complex process that requires a lot of time and effort. There are various reasons that contribute to increased motivation to learn foreign languages [2]. Some of them are practical. Others are intellectual. Still others may seem sentimental.

№	Factors	Opportunities
	Work	Knowing a foreign language helps a person find a more perspective job, get a promotion, go on a business trip to another country, conclude profitable contracts, increase incomes. In any area of our activity - education, industry, commerce, international tourism, computer technology, etc. – knowing foreign languages will be productive.[3]
2	Science	If a person knows foreign language, one can have useful information from foreign sources and have access to more extensive knowledge. In the context of expanding ties with foreign countries and the internationalization of scientific knowledge, a well-organized system of international information is of particular importance, the normal functioning of which is unthinkable without specialists who really know foreign languages, who are able to quickly extract information from foreign sources without a translator, present it in their native language and use it in scientific work. Teaching foreign languages has become a social order of society and a necessary condition for the effective work of the scientific and scientific-technical integration.
3	Education	Application for the foreign University into a single educational space opens up new prospects for studying abroad. Culture - literature, feature films,

		television programs, music, belonging to the culture of a particular country, will become even more accessible if you know the language.
4	Immigration	Knowing a foreign language makes the process of adaptation and integration into local society easier and faster.
5	Travelling	Long distances are no longer a hindrance, as they were in the last century. Everyone travels and communicates. Even a minimal knowledge of a foreign language helps to “hold out” in a foreign country: buy food or tickets, get to the right place, communicate with new people.
6	Personal motives	international marriages (knowing the language makes communication easier), back to roots (for example, teaching children the language to preserve family traditions or to preserve the language), friends (knowing the language will make communication easier, will help to better understand another way of thinking).

Safeguarding the linguistic heritage of humanity and promoting expression, creativity and the dissemination of ideas in as many languages as possible [4]. Encouraging linguistic diversity – while respecting the mother tongue – at all levels of education wherever possible, and the study of several languages from the earliest possible age.

It is accepted that learning a foreign language for the Uzbek youngsters may provide with in various spheres such as work, science, education, immigration, travelling, personal motives leading to personal and social development. If the Uzbek young generation will study foreign languages, they will have innovational and creative ideas which benefit to the prosperity of our country.

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